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Press Release

Towards a deterministic 6G network: reliable, time sensitive and predictable

The consortium of **"PREDICT-6G - "PRogrammable AI-Enabled Deterministic neTworking for 6G"** is delighted to announce the start of this initiative funded by the **European Commission** under the **Horizon Europe** Research and Innovation programme.

The **PREDICT-6G** project aims to create a secure, modular, interoperable, and extensible deterministic network and management framework that automates the definition, provisioning, monitoring, fulfillment, and life-cycle management of end-to-end (E2E) deterministic services over multiple network domains. PREDICT-6G's mission is therefore set towards the development of an E2E 6G solution including architecture and protocols that can guarantee seamless provisioning of services for vertical use cases requiring extremely tight timing and reliability constraints.

PREDICT-6G builds on top of three pillars:

- To **extend the reliability and time sensitiveness features** of IEEE 802.11 and 3GPP networks, including APIs for the monitoring and control of such capabilities, enabling predictability.
- To **develop a Multi-technology multi-domain Data-Plane** jointly with an AI-driven multi-stakeholder inter-domain Control-Plane.
- To **enhance the predictability of the network through intelligence**, enabling the forecasting of the occupancy of network resources and the effect of accepting a new flow into the network.

PREDICT-6G will develop a novel multi-technology multi-domain Data-Plane overhauling the reliability and time sensitive design features existing in current wired and wireless standards.

Applications and use cases that benefit from such networking capabilities include, among others, audio and video streaming, industrial automation, cloud robotics,

Internet of Things (IoT), Digital Twins (DT), and connected vehicles. Additionally, **the whole set of 6G network stakeholders will benefit** from a network that behaves in a predictable way, capable of forecasting possible congestion issues and anticipating them, so the application and network control mechanisms are never compromised.

PREDICT-6G will validate the results in **three use cases**, carefully selected to represent application needs and relevant technological gaps. In addition, several unit tests of specific technologies will be performed on two open labs:

- 1) Deterministic services for critical communications at the Nokia Budapest Open Lab;
- 2) Multi-domain deterministic communication at the Madrid Open Lab (5TONIC);
- 3) Smart Manufacturing at the Ericsson Madrid Open Lab (5TONIC).

During the **kick-off meeting** that took place on the **10-11 of January 2023** in Madrid, the partners set the roadmap for the next 30 months of work. The change in the current networking paradigm will be key in powering up the waited for digitalisation of the industry and fostering Europe´s leadership in 6G.

PREDiCT-6G consortium, led by Universidad Carlos III de Madrid (UC3M), consists of 17 prominent partners from seven Member States. Meet [here](#) all the partners involved in this ambitious project.

Learn more about **PREDICT-6G** and contact us!

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the European Union